

Assessment of the level of formation of values of healthy lifestyle of students

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Purpose: *theoretically substantiate, develop and experimentally test a system for assessing the level of formation of the values of a healthy lifestyle of students in the process of physical education.*

Material & Methods: *to achieve this goal, such research methods were used – analysis and synthesis of literature sources and documentary materials, pedagogical observation, pedagogical testing, pedagogical experiment, sociological research methods (questioning), anthropometry method, methods for determining the functional state of the body, methods for assessing the level of physical health (according to G. L. Apanasenko method), methods for determining motor activity, testing theoretical knowledge, methods of mathematical statistics. The study involved 108 students and 120 female students of higher educational institutions in Kyiv.*

Results: *the components of the students' value attitude to a healthy lifestyle are defined and the criteria and indicators of their formation are refined: cognitive (knowledge about health, healthy lifestyle, health values, axiological attitudes to achieve the goal), motivational and value (attitude to one's own health, positive emotions, interest and needs for a healthy lifestyle), activity (actions and behavior, contribute to a healthy lifestyle, compliance with the requirements of a healthy lifestyle in everyday life). On the basis of certain criteria and indicators, the levels of formation of the values of a healthy lifestyle are characterized: high, sufficient, satisfactory and critical. It was revealed that the majority of students have a critical level of formation of values of a healthy lifestyle (boys – 75,93%, girls – 72,5%).*

Conclusion: *the existing developments in assessing the attitude of students towards a healthy lifestyle and the development of their attitude towards recreational activities have been further developed; based on the analysis of empirical research data, a significant discrepancy was noted between the declared value of health, a healthy lifestyle, and behavioral attitudes of students. On the basis of the obtained data, we proposed the directions of modernization of physical education of students, to promote the formation of values of a healthy lifestyle.*

Keywords: *students, health, healthy lifestyle, values, motor activity, assessment system.*

Introduction

The problem of youth health, its social, medical, pedagogical, and psychological aspects have gained national importance and require additional intensification of the search for new effective directions in developing health-forming technologies [11; 21]. Today, the health of the young generation is one of the most important indicators of a healthy potential of the nation, therefore its preservation and strengthening are of priority [2; 7; 18]. This issue is actively discussed not only among scientists [8; 12; 23], but is also an important area of state policy of Ukraine, as evidenced by the development and implementation at the legislative level of relevant programs and projects [14–17]. The program-regulatory documents draw attention to the development of a conscious attitude of young people to their health and the health of others, the formation of the fundamentals and hygienic skills of a healthy lifestyle, the need to preserve and strengthen their physical and mental health, and the promotion of a healthy lifestyle (HLS).

A theoretical analysis of research on the formation of values of a healthy lifestyle of university students has made it possible to determine the high interest of specialists in attracting students to a healthy lifestyle and the degree of study of the scientific problem in modern scientific literature [2; 5; 13]. Scientists see

the possibility of solving problems associated with the formation of values of a healthy lifestyle, based on the introduction of models of health formative activities, acquires the character of value orientation, that is, determines the mind, activity and behavior of students in various life situations, in solving personal problems, reflects the process of accumulation and generalization of individual experience of an individual on himself and his health [8; 12]. At the same time, it is noted that due to the imperfect software and methodological support of the educational process on physical education, insufficient information about health, the formative activity and the conditions for its use in the educational process on physical education in the framework of educational and extracurricular activities of educational institutions address the issues of value formation healthy way of life of students has not found an adequate practical solution, identified the need for further research [1; 4; 9; 13; 18].

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Material and Methods of the research

The analysis of the scientific and methodological literature

was carried out with the aim of theoretical substantiation of the object of research, as well as the generalization of the scientific approaches to assessing the values of the healthy lifestyles of students in the process of physical education. The theoretical analysis, generalization of modern practical experience made it possible to determine the relevance of the study, clarify and specify the goals, objectives and orientation of the pedagogical experiment, develop the content of a comprehensive program of research of value orientations, motives, interests and needs of students for classes using recreational motor activity, physical condition indicators, morbidity, level of motor activity, theoretical preparedness of students about the formation of health.

One of the main methods of the study was a pedagogical experiment, which was introduced in order to obtain the initial data, became the basis for the development of a system for assessing the values of the healthy lifestyles of students. Evaluated the health status and morbidity structure of students. Anthropometric studies of students were carried out with standard equipment according to generally accepted and unified methods [19]. Studies on morbidity and disease resistance were carried out according to the results of in-depth medical examinations by copying information from primary medical records of educational institutions. Additionally, we took into account the number of student's absences due to illness, the duration of one case of illness. In the study of morbidity processing of the materials carried by classes of diseases in accordance with the "International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Problems" (ICD-10) [20]. In determining the methods of health assessment in the study, they preferred the most adequate, informative, non-invasive and such that they provide an opportunity to cover a group of students in a short period of time, therefore the assessment of the level of health was carried out using the express method of somatic health G. L. Apanasenko [3]. To assess the attitude of students to physical education classes, motivational priorities in the choice of types of motor activity, sociological research methods (questioning) were used. The basis for the development of an assessment of the level of formation of value orientations was a modified research method Yu. S. Boyko [5]. To determine the initial level of formation of attitudes towards a healthy lifestyle among students, the method of M. Rokich "Value Orientations" is used, which allows to investigate the orientation of the individual and determine his attitude to the world, to other people, to himself, the perception of the world, key motives of actions. Material systematization and initial mathematical processing were performed using Microsoft® Excel 2010 tables.

The studies were conducted at the bases of the Kyiv National Linguistic University, National Pedagogical University named after M. P. Dragomanov. The study involved 108 male students and 120 female students. The student contingent was involved in the study voluntarily with the written consent to participate in all stages of the pedagogical experiment, as well as to further analyze and disclose their personal data when considering and reporting on the research results.

Results of the research

Analyzing the results of the study [5] on the formation of a healthy lifestyle of university students, we have identified the following components that characterize it: affective, motivational, informative, projective, activity and procedural. The

affective component reflects the peculiarities of students' attitudes towards preserving and strengthening their health by observing the principles of a healthy lifestyle, and the motivational one indicates a desire to expand knowledge in the field of health, interest in the formation and strengthening of planning skills and organizing health saving skills. Note that when evaluating the affective component, we, taking into account the refinements of predecessors [5], drew attention to the location of the category "Health" in the rating of terminal values. If this category was located in the top five, we accounted for 5 points, in case it occupied from 6 to 9 places – 4 points, from 10 to 13 – 4 points, and when it was placed from 14 to 18 positions – 2 points. The substantive component assumes that students have the necessary amount of knowledge on the basics of a healthy lifestyle, while the projective component focuses on the planning skills of individual events. But the activity component is associated with the observance by students of the optimal motor mode. The purpose of the procedural component is the practical application of the principles of a healthy lifestyle in everyday life, as a result of which one can assess the level of physical health of the participants in the experiment. Thus, the general level of formation of a healthy lifestyle of students depends on the level of formation of its individual components. These components were used as the basis for the criteria for the formation of a healthy lifestyle for university students.

We carried out the assessment of the formation of a healthy lifestyle of students of higher educational institutions on the basis of the criteria developed, taking into account the indicators characterizing it. These indicators included the awareness of the need to comply with the fundamentals of a healthy lifestyle, an understanding of the primary value of health, knowledge and skills in matters of a healthy lifestyle, as well as the implementation of appropriate steps aimed at maintaining a healthy lifestyle.

The results of a study aimed at determining the level of theoretical knowledge of students convincingly indicate that the majority of students have fragmentary knowledge concerning health, a healthy lifestyle, and its components. The lack of fundamental knowledge among students has been noted by us in matters relating to the rational mode of the day, hardening, nutrition, etc. The main reason for the students' lack of awareness in matters relating to the health of formative activities is, first of all, the lack of effectiveness of the physical education process as an integral part general structure of education of student youth.

In the future, the criteria served us to establish the levels of formation of a healthy lifestyle of students, including high, sufficient, satisfactory and critical. Thus, on the basis of the selected components, in the course of the study, we developed an integrated assessment of the formation of a healthy lifestyle for students of higher educational institutions (Table 1).

On the basis of the proposed approach, we identified the following levels of the formation of a healthy lifestyles of university students (Table 2).

So, with the development of a healthy lifestyle of students in further research, we considered this gradation:

– "high" level provided for a high dominance of health in the system of terminal values, high motivation for a healthy life-

Table 1

Integral assessment of the development of a healthy lifestyle of university students

Criterion	Component	Quantitative score, points	Score on scale	Points
Value-motivational	affectionate: attitude to health	14–18	health is highly dominant	5
		10–13	sufficient dominance	4
		6–9	average dominance	3
		1–5	low dominance	2
	motivational: motivation for healthy lifestyles	5	sustainable motivation	5
		4	sufficient	4
		3	established	3
		2	missing	2
Cognitive	informative: volume of knowledge on healthy lifestyles	12–10	high level of knowledge	5
		9–7	sufficient	4
		6–4	average	3
		3–1	elementary	2
	projective: individual event planning skills	5	high level of skills	5
		4	sufficient level of skills	4
		3	average	3
Activity-procedural	activity: daily energy consumption	40 and more	high level of MA	5
		37–40	average	4
		33–37	low	3
		less 33	very low	2
	procedural: level of physical health	more 16	high level	5
		12–16	above the average	4
		7–12	average	4
		4–7	below the average	3
less 4	low	2		

style at the level of belief, in-depth knowledge of the fundamentals of a healthy lifestyle, and planning skills for health measures, adherence to optimal motor regimen and proper behavioral stereotypes;

– "sufficient" level – accountable realize the value of health, the necessary knowledge of the basics of a healthy lifestyle and the ability to plan activities *zdorovyaformuvannya*, steady motivation to comply with the principles of a healthy lifestyle, the average level of physical activity and responsible attitude to health;

– "satisfactory" level of development of a healthy lifestyle indicates an insufficient value attitude to health and the presence of motivation to observe certain principles of a healthy lifestyle, the presence of a certain amount of knowledge in the field of healthy lifestyle and the ability to plan individual health activities of the formation, a low level of physical activity and irregular adherence to basic components of a healthy lifestyle;

– "critical" level indicates a low dominance of the category "health" in the system of life values, the lack of positive motivation for a healthy lifestyle, lack of knowledge and skills to plan health measures, a low level of physical activity and non-compliance with the principles of a healthy lifestyle.

The components that make up the formation of a healthy lifestyle of students were studied. The study showed that the average value was equal to (5; 3; 9,5; 3,97 points) for the affective component of the value-motivational criterion for young men, and (3; 3; 4; 0,77 points) for the motivational component. According to the informative component of the cognitive criterion, the indicator was (4; 3; 5; 1,81 points), and by the

Table 2

Scale of the level of formation of a healthy lifestyle of students

Level	Quantitative score	Points
High	30–27	5
Sufficient	26–23	4
Satisfactory	22–19	3
Critical	18–16	2

projective component – (3; 2; 3; 0,7 points). According to the activity component of the activity-procedural criterion – (33,9; 32,26; 34,76; 1,98 c.u.); and according to procedural – (4,52; 0; 7; 3,54 c.u.) (Table 3).

The girls had the following average indicators: affective component – (4; 2; 5,5; 2,7 points), for motivational – (4; 3; 4; 0,93 points), for informative – (5; 4; 6; 5; 2,07 points), by projectives – (3; 3; 4; 0,77 points), for activities – (31; 29; 33; 2,79 c.u.), and by procedural – (4; 0; 7; 3,48 c.u.).

The distribution of participants in the experiment according to the level of formation of healthy lifespan showed that among young men, 3,7% (n=4) had a sufficient level, 20,37% (n=22) were satisfactory and 75,93% were critical (n=82) (Figure 1).

At the same time, girls were characterized by such a distribution by levels of formation of healthy lifestyles: a sufficient level of 2,5% (n=3), satisfactory 25% (n=30), critical 72,5% (n=87). As we can see, among boys there is a 1,2% decrease in the proportion sufficient and 3,43% less with a critical level, but a 4,86% increase in the proportion with an average level of the formation of healthy lifestyles than girls. However, it

Table 3

Indicators of the formation of a healthy lifestyle of university students, n=228

Components, score	Boys, n=108				Girl, n=120			
	Me	25%	75%	S	Me	25%	75%	S
Affective	5,00	3,00	9,50	3,97	4,00	2,00	5,50	2,70
Motivational	3,00	3,00	4,00	0,77	4,00	3,00	4,00	0,93
Informative	4,00	3,00	5,00	1,81	5,00	4,00	6,50	2,07
Projective	3,00	2,00	3,00	0,70	3,00	3,00	4,00	0,77
Activity	33,90	32,26	34,76	1,98	31,00	29,00	33,00	2,79
Procedural	4,52	0,00	7,00	3,54	4,00	0,00	7,00	3,48

should be noted that there were no statistically significant differences in the distribution of subjects by gender ($p>0,05$). As a result of the study, no students with a high level of formation of values of a healthy lifestyle were established. This requires the development of measures aimed at improving the level of formation of the values of healthy lifestyles of students in the process of physical education.

Figure 1. Assessment of the level of formation of values of a healthy lifestyle of university students, (boys n=108; girls n=120):
■ – sufficient; ■ – satisfactory; ■ – critical

Conclusions / Discussion

We have confirmed the data of researchers [5; 8; 12; 13; etc.] that the process of formation of values of a healthy lifestyle of students in higher education institutions is due to the current system of physical education, which today requires substantial reorganization and improvement. These problems in the organization of physical education of students of higher educational institutions naturally lead to a deterioration in the level of involvement of young people in regular physical activity classes, a decrease in their physical health and physical preparedness indicators [2; 6; 7; 10; 23]. Training sessions do not provide the volume of physical activity necessary for students [4]. 61,1% of respondents consider their knowledge and skills to use physical culture aids to implement measures to preserve their own health insufficient. Similar research results were obtained by us. In the physical education of students, a problematic situation has arisen, which is the contradiction between the level

of social requirements and the effectiveness of the system of physical education. Thus, the majority of surveyed students of higher educational institutions do not consider themselves competent in matters of health protection, 5% could not answer this question and only 30% admit their competence. The results of a study aimed at determining the level of theoretical knowledge of students convincingly indicate that the majority of students have fragmentary knowledge concerning health, healthy lifestyles and its components [9; 12]. The lack of fundamental knowledge among students has been noted by us in matters relating to the rational mode of the day, hardening, nutrition, etc. The main reason for the students' lack of awareness in matters relating to health-forming activities is, first of all, the lack of effectiveness of the physical education process as an integral part of the general structure of education student youth. The data we have obtained confirms the existing scientific developments and determines the need to substantiate approaches to improving the level of theoretical preparedness of students in health preservation as part of the formation of healthy benefits.

Scientific findings confirm the results of our study [7; 11; 18; 23 etc.] on the practical absence of students with a safe level of health. The criteria for assessing the levels of formation of values of a healthy lifestyle of students have been improved, a qualitative and quantitative characteristic of the levels of formation of values of healthy lifestyle of students (high, sufficient, satisfactory, critical) has been submitted. The components of the students' value attitude to a healthy lifestyle are defined and the criteria and indicators of their formation are refined: cognitive (knowledge about health, healthy lifestyle, health values, axiological goals for achieving the goal), motivational and value (attitude to one's own health, positive emotions, interest and needs for a healthy lifestyle), activity (actions and behavior, contribute to a healthy lifestyle, compliance with the requirements of a healthy lifestyle in everyday life). On the basis of certain criteria and indicators, the levels of formation of the values of a healthy lifestyle are characterized: high, sufficient, satisfactory and critical. It was found that most students have a critical level of formation of healthy lifestyle values (boys 75,93%, girls 72,5%).

Prospects for further research and this direction will be the possibility of applying the developed approaches to assessing the values of a healthy lifestyle for students of general secondary education institutions.

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